

Situational Analysis on the Processed Potato Products Industry in Sri Lanka

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Abstract

Potato (*Solanum tuberosum*) serves as a crucial food crop and processing raw material in Sri Lanka. This review examines the status of Sri Lanka's potato industry, from cultivation through processing to final products. Three districts, Nuwara Eliya, Badulla, and Jaffna, dominate local production, with Granola variety comprising 90% of cultivation. The industry faces challenges including limited local production capacity, heavy reliance on imports, and quality control issues in processing. Local processing includes frozen French fries, potato chips, extruded snacks, and crackers, with very few companies leading production. Critical control points in processing include temperature management, oil quality monitoring, and metal detection. The review identifies opportunities for industry growth through improved varieties, enhanced cold storage facilities, and better-quality management systems. Recommendations include developing heat-tolerant varieties, implementing zero-balance stock systems, and strengthening regulatory frameworks for food safety.

Keywords : Potato, Sri Lankan Potato industry, Processed potato products, Potato cultivation

1. Introduction

Potatoes have emerged as the world's fourth most important staple food crop after rice, maize and wheat. It is cultivated on 17,578,672 ha, around the world producing 370.437 million Mt in 2019 (FAOSTAT, 2021). The potato production of Asia was around 189.810 million Mt, whilst the potato production of Europe, America, Africa and Oceania was recorded as 107.265 million Mt, 45.084 million Mt, 26.534 million Mt and 1.743 million Mt respectively, as of 2019 according to FAOSTAT, 2021. Potato is grown by more than 100 countries in the world while currently, China, India, Ukraine, Russia and the United States of America contribute to a major share of the total world potato production. China was the largest producer of potatoes in 2019, with an annual production of 91.881 million Mt. Asia and Europe are the world's major potato producing regions.

Rank	Country	Production Thousand Tonnes/year
1.	China	78237
2.	China, mainland	78184
3.	India	51300
4.	Ukraine	20838
5.	Russian Federation	19607
6.	United States of America	18790
7.	Germany	11715
8.	Bangladesh	9606
9.	France	8692
10.	Poland	7849

Table 1 Top potato producers of the world 2020

Source: FAOSTAT 2021

Potatoes are a subsidiary food item consumed as a vegetable in Sri Lanka. Potatoes are known as a main item in the country's food basket. It has emerged as one of the most important food crops in Sri Lanka mainly due to its high consumer preference and high net return. Potato is considered the best nutritional vegetable considering its dry matter content, edible energy and protein content and is proven to be useful in achieving nutritional security.

In Sri Lanka, potato cultivation is highly concentrated in the up country, whereas it is extensively cultivated in Nuwara Eliya and Badulla districts. Jaffna is the other district where potatoes are grown to a lesser extent.

District	Extent (Ha)	Production (Mt)
Kandy	5	68
Nuwara Eliya	1,379	28,181
Badulla	2,090	35,729
Jaffna	90	1,105
Vavuniya	0.1	1.3

Table 2 Extent of potato cultivation in the country according to the district

Source: HORTI

The consumption of potatoes depends on the total production and heavily on the imported quantity of potatoes. The following is a graph comparing the potato production, import quantity of potatoes and thus the total availability.

The major growing areas of potatoes in Sri Lanka are, Badulla, Nuwara Eliya, Jaffna, etc. Badulla and Nuwara Eliya districts are the major potato growing districts in Sri Lanka. Jaffna is the other district where the potato is grown. The potato cultivation in Jaffna is of a lesser extent during Maha season. In Badulla district, potatoes are cultivated in lowlands and on highlands during Yala and Maha seasons respectively. Welimada and Uva Paranagama are the main potato growing regions in Badulla district. In Nuwara Eliya potato is cultivated in two major seasons, Maha and Yala in areas like, Lindula, Thalawakele, Kandapola, Ragala and Pattipola.

Figure 1 Potato growing districts in Sri Lanka

Source: department of census and statistics

In terms of the production of potato, it increased from 2000 to 2002 and has shown a decreasing trend thereafter until 2010. According to the department of agriculture, the reasons for this decline were adverse weather conditions, shortage of quality seed potatoes and high prices of imported seed potatoes during the period. However, an increasing trend was recorded from 2011 to 2016 mainly with the sharp increase in the production in Maha season.

Figure 2 Production of potatoes in seasons

Source: department of census and statistics

In Sri Lanka the 90% cultivated variety is **Granola**. Other varieties were developed as **heat tolerant** varieties for Jaffna, Kalpitiya, Puttalam areas. Some of such varieties that were developed and now are successfully grown include Sashy, Luplas, Ranomu and Arnova. There are some failed types of developed varieties which were trialed by the department of agriculture such as, Golden star, Yield star, Seetha and Krushi

Seed Potato Quality and Safety in Sri Lanka

Seed potato certification: according to the 2003 No 22-parliament gazette in Sri Lanka, the label of the seed potato must contain the name of the crop, registration number, seed type, weight, variety, manufactured and expiry dates, seed lot number, propagation percentage, date of harvesting and minimum purity percentage. The Seed Potato Center at Seetha Eliya, Sri Lanka maintains the seed potato quality and provides seed potatoes for the farmers.

Pesticide and chemicals used in seed potato production

The seed potato production in the seed potato farms are conducted in a specific manner with the cold storage of 4-degree temperature and a humidity between 90-95% ensuring propagation. The pesticides and chemicals used in seed potato production are as follows.

Dilution Rate	Component	Application
25g/ 10 L	Seed potato Potato tubers	40-50g/100 kg of seed potatoes Pre growth stage 800-1000g/ha Post growth stage 1200-1500g/ha

There are various field standards for seed potato classes. This grading system allows quality potato crop cultivation through high quality seed potatoes.

Requirements of seed potato storage

Gradual cooling of potato must be done to cool potato from harvested temperature to 4 ° C. Storage must be up to 6 months, because dormancy of potato breaks after 6 months. In normal temperature breaking of dormancy only takes 3 months. Then temperature of potatoes must be increased to room temperature gradually (1 ° C per day)

Figure 3 Temperature control board at Seetha Eliya seed potato farm

Figure 4 Labelled seed potato lots ready to be dispatched into the cold storage conditions for propagation

Potato tuber quality and safety

MRLs for potato tubers specified by the control of pesticides Act No. 33 of 1980

Pesticide	Time limit (days)	MRL mg/kg
Thiacloprid	14	0.02
Abamectin	14	0.01
Acetamiprid	14	0.03
Thiamethoxan	14	0.3

Captan	14	0.05
Thiram	14	0.2
Chlorothalonil	14	0.2
Dimethomorph	14	0.05
Fipronil	14	0.02
Macozeb	14	0.2
Metiram	14	0.2
Propamocarb	14	0.3
Propineb	14	0.2
Prothiophos	21	0.05

Table 3 MRLs for potato tubers specified by the control of pesticides Act No. 33 of 1980

Raw potatoes are rarely tested for allergens, toxins and pesticide residues as there are less to no evidence found related to the potato hazards related to raw potato tubers. Some of the major concerns related to potato toxins are; alpha solanine, alpha chaconine and patatine.

The test methods to quantify alpha solanine and alpha chaconine is less utilized. While the mainly used test methods includes, ELISA, HPLC, HPLC with Mass spectrometry, HPTLC (High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography), etc.

The HPTLC method is as follows, Alpha-solanine and alpha-chaconine were extracted from dehydrated potatoes through boiling methanol-acetic acid (95 + 5, v/v). The analytes are separated on a silica gel 60 F254 HPTLC plate by a saturated mixture of dichloromethane- methanol-water-concentrated ammonium hydroxide (70 + 30 + 4 + 0.4, v/v), which is used for vertical development of the plate up to a distance of 85 mm. For visualization, the plate is dipped 3 times into a modified carr-Price reagent, 20% (w/v) antimony(III) chloride in acetic acid-dichloromethane (1 + 3, v/v), and subsequently heated on a hot plate at 105 degrees C for 5 min.

In terms with potato grading, according to size and shape potatoes are graded for relevant products. As for an example, large uniform shaped potatoes are usually selected for frozen French fries production. Disease, damage or pest attacked potatoes are selected and removed to ensure safety and quality of the raw potatoes for consumption and processing.

Local Potato Value Chain

Figure 5 local potato value chain

Marketing Channel of Potato Suppliers

Figure 6 Marketing channel of potato suppliers

2. Local Potato Processed Products Industry

2.1 Product Characteristics

Local Frozen French Fries

CCPs considered in Local Frozen French Fries industry:

- **Cleaning & Sorting:** Sort out potatoes based on their size (min 75mm diameter)
- **Blanching and Centrifugal De-watering:** Monitoring blanching machines with hot water, 60-80°C, 5-8 minutes (CCP)
- **Hot air-drying line:** In Air cooling/drying systems with conveyor belts [175°C, 5-20 min (CCP)]
- **Frying:** Consistent oil temperature as a critical control point, 150-170°C for 15-60 seconds, turn over time 5 hours (CCP)
- **Blast Freezing and Packaging:** Blast freezing temperature and time as a critical control point (-30)- (-35) °C, 30-50 minutes per batch (CCP)
- **Cold storage:** Store in -18°C or below (CCP) with temperature control

Product description and intended use according to HACCP

Item	Product Description
Product description	Fresh potato slices 7mm cross section, no flavors added, Vegetable oil, Salt
Physical Properties	Product should be free from rancidity, undesirable odor and slices color $\geq 55L$
Chemical Characteristics	Moisture (3%), Oil (40%), salt before seasoning (3%), Ash (4%) and Free fatty acid (FFA) (1.5%) as oleic oil.
Microbiological Characteristics	Product should be free from microorganisms and pathogenic microbes which causing poisoning and their toxin, bacteria count 50000 cfu, Bacillus count maximum 10000 cfu.
Nutritional Value Serving size 100g	Calories 157 Total fat 3g, 45% Daily value Sodium 236 mg, 10% Total carbohydrates 29g, 39% Protein 4g Salt 0.6g Sugar <0.25g
Storage conditions	Store -18°C or below and away from sunlight
Distribution methods	Supermarkets, restaurants, retails, malls and hotels
Shelf life	6 months
Consumer requirements	Ready for consumption for all ages, direct consumption, take the product out of the freezer and keep for about 2-3 minutes, deep fry the frozen French fries at 175-180°C hot oil for 5-6 minutes, do not refreeze after thawing

Table 4 Product description according to HACCP

Product Description and Intended Use According to HACCP

Item	Product description	
Product name	Fresh slice potato frying in vegetarian oil	
Product description	Potato slices 8 flavors (chili- cheese-salt - salt &vinegar -spicy cheese - kebab- chicken - ketchup)	
Physical properties	Product should be free from rancidity, undesirable odor and slices color ≥55L	
Chemical characteristics	Moisture (3%), Oil (40%), salt before seasoning (3%), Ash (4%)and Free fatty acid (FFA) (1.5%) as oleic oil.	
Microbiological characteristics	Product should be free from microorganisms and pathogenic microbes which causing poisoning and their toxin, bacteria count 50000 cfu, Bacillus count maximum 10000 cfu.	
	Parameters	Amount (gm)
	Fat	3.94
	Protein	0.67
	Carbohydrate	4.27
	Saturated fat	1.22
	Un Saturated fat	2.72
Nutritional value	Cholesterol	0.0
/10gm	Fiber	1.12
	Vitamin A	0.0
	Vitamin C	0.003
	Sodium	0.05
	Calcium	0.003
	Iron	0.003
	Calories /10g	65.27 kcal
Raw& packing material	Potato – palm oleic oil - flavor - film PPM 40μ - Carton single B - printing rolls - adhesive rolls - a starch roll.	
Stock keeping unitsSKUs	13-17 mg , 24-28gm, 62-72gm.	
Storage conditions	Store in a cool and dry place away from sunlight.	
Distribution method	Malls - supermarkets - restaurants - retails - big markets.	
Shelf life	6 months.	
Customer requirements	Direct consumption.	
Intended Use/targetgroup	Ready for consumption for all ages.	

Table 5 Intended use according to HACCP

Quality Inspection Specifications of French Fries

Characteristics		Specification
String Length	% of ≥ 3"	30% min. (per # of sticks)
	% of ≥ 3-2"	70% min. (per # of sticks)
	Slivers & Shorts (<2")	2% max. (per # of sticks)
Presence of Black/Grey/Green Pieces/ Spots		5 pcs/500g max.
Presence of Impurities/ any Foreign Matters		Nil
Temperature Condition		Frozen (-18°C)
Shelf Life		1 1/2 Years
Sensory Parameters	Surface Color	Crispy to Bite, Not Crunchy
	Outer Texture	Light Resistance to Bite
	Inner Texture	Typical French Fries Aroma
	Aroma	Typical French Fries Flavor
	Flavor	Typical French Fries Flavor

Table 6 Quality Inspection Specifications of French Fries

Microbiological analysis of potato slices before and after frying for two processing lines

Microbiological tests (cfu // gm)	Processing line	Result before frying	Result after frying	Specification
Total plate count	1	3.6 ×10 ^{6a}	10×10 ^b	≤50000
	2	2.7×10 ^{6b}	7×10 ^c	
Mold & yeast	1	9.0×10 ^{5c}	1×10 ^d	≤500
	2	6.6×10 ^{5d}	20×10 ^a	
Staphylococcus aureus	1	Nil ^h	Nil ^e	Nil
	2	Nil ^h	Nil ^e	
Bacillus cereus	1	3.2×10 ^{3e}	Nil ^e	≤10000
	2	5.2×10 ^{2f}	Nil ^e	
E. Coli	1	1.2×10 ^{2g}	Nil ^e	≤10
	2	2.7×10^{2g}	Nil^e	

Table 7 Microbiological Analysis of potato slices

*cfu / 1gm = colony forming units per gram.

*The limits are according (E.S: 1629:2017).

Values followed by different letter in columns are significantly different at p<0.05.

Potato Chips

CCPs:

- Frying quality of the oil – TPM should below 24%
- Frying temperature is 165⁰C-175⁰C and for 2.45 -3.45 minutes
- Metal detection

HACCP Flowsheet for Potato Chips and French Fries

Stage	Hazards/reasons	Preventative measures	Critical factors/limits/controls
1. RAW MATERIALS RECEIPT POTATOES	MICROBIOLOGICAL Fungi, Molds, Bacteria CHEMICAL Fungicides and Pesticides PHYSICAL Foreign materials from soil, harvesting	Suppliers of potatoes (SQA) Inspection of suppliers for hygiene	Control of safety specifications Limits of fungicide and pesticide residues (MRLs - EC directives) Control for foreign materials
OIL/FATS	CHEMICAL Residues of Fungicides and Pesticides Additives Heavy metals	Suppliers of potatoes (SQA) Inspection of suppliers for hygiene	Control of specifications Limit of antifoams: 0.04 mg/Kg Limit of heavy metals: 2%
FLAVORING MATERIALS, SALT, ADDITIVES AND PRESERVATIVES	CHEMICAL Residues of chemicals PHYSICAL Foreign materials	Suppliers of materials (SQA)	Control of safety specifications Limits for chemical residues (according to EC legislation)
WATER	MICROBIOLOGICAL Pathogens: Salmonella, Shigella, Leptospira, E. Coli, Pasturella, Vibrio, Cholerae, Yersinia enterocolica, Mycobacterium tuberculosis Molds and Bacteria CHEMICAL Organic compounds Radioisotopes Heavy metal PHYSICAL Foreign materials from soil	Cleaning and disinfection of water	Control of specifications (according to Dir. 98/83/EC) Limits for pathogens and chemical contaminants (according to Dir. 98/83/EC)

Stage	Hazards/reasons	Preventative measures	Critical factors/limits/controls
2. STORAGE OF RAW MATERIALS			
POTATOES	MICROBIOLOGICAL Fungi: Phytophthora infestans, Alternaria solani, Fusarium sambucinum, Fusarium coeruleum, Verticillium alboatrum, Verticillium dahliae, Helminthosporium solani, Spongopora subterranean f. Sp. ubterranean Viruses: : Annulus dubius Holmes, Marnor solani Bacteria: Pseudomonas solanacearum, Streptomyces scabies, Erwinia carotovora ssp. Atroseptica, Carotovora, Erwinia carotovora ssp. Atroseptica, Pseudomonas marginalis, Clostridium sp., Corynebacterium sepedonicum CHEMICAL Chemicals used to control vegetation	GMP - GHP Hygienic conditions during storage Cleaning and disinfection of storage area Use of pallets to allow ventilation Ventilation system Pest control programs Personnel hygiene	Control of storage conditions RH: 90-100%, T=3-10° C Concentration of : O ₂ < 18%, CO ₂ < 5% Inspection of hygiene during storage Inspection of programs: pest control, cleaning and disinfection of storage area Solanine: max 0.555% dry matter of potato - increase during storage: 20 mg/100g Control for residues of chemicals used to control vegetation
OIL/FATS	CHEMICAL Oxidation components in oil/fat (in order to be more stable in oxidation during frying) PHYSICAL Foreign materials	GMP - GHP Cleaning and disinfection of oil silo Pest control programs Prevention of oil from air and light	Control of storage conditions T ≤ 0 ° C Control of oils/fats deterioration Peroxide and p-Anisidine Value < 3-5 meq/Kg
FLAVORING MATERIALS, SALT, ADDITIVES & PRESERVATIVES	PHYSICAL Foreign materials	GMP - GHP Conditions during storage Pest control programs Cleaning of storage area	Control of storage conditions Inspection of programs: pest control, cleaning of storage area

Stage	Hazards/reasons	Preventative measures	Critical factors/limits/controls
3. CONVEYING OF RAW MATERIALS	MICROBIOLOGICAL Microorganisms from surfaces PHYSICAL Foreign materials	GMP - GHP Cleaning and disinfection of equipment Cleaning agents approved for foods	Control of cleaning and disinfection programs for surfaces and equipment
4. POTATO WASHING	MICROBIOLOGICAL Microorganism from equipment, water CHEMICAL Residues of cleaning agents in the equipment PHYSICAL Foreign materials	GMP - GHP Assurance of hygienic conditions Cleaning and disinfection of equipment Renewal of water	Microbiological control of water Control of washing efficiency Control of cleaning and disinfection programs Control of reuse of water
5. PEELING AND TRIMMING	MICROBIOLOGICAL Microorganism from equipment, surfaces CHEMICAL Residues of cleaning agents in the equipment and lubricants PHYSICAL Foreign materials (from metallic surfaces)	GMP - GHP Assurance of hygienic conditions Cleaning and disinfection of equipment Maintenance of equipment Lubricant approved for foods	Control of cleaning and disinfection programs Control for foreign materials and draw away
6. SELECTING AND SLICING	MICROBIOLOGICAL Microorganism from equipment, personnel CHEMICAL Residues of cleaning agents in the equipment PHYSICAL Foreign materials (from metallic surfaces)	GMP - GHP Assurance of hygienic conditions Cleaning and disinfection of equipment Lubricant approved for foods Maintenance of equipment Personnel training	Microbiological control Control of cleaning and disinfection programs Control for foreign material and draw away Removal of potatoes with defects

Stage	Hazards/reasons	Preventative measures	Critical factors/limits/controls
7. POTATO WASHING & 8. BLANCHING	MICROBIOLOGICAL Microorganism from water, equipment CHEMICAL Residues of cleaning agents PHYSICAL Foreign materials	GMP - GHP Assurance of hygienic conditions Cleaning and disinfection of equipment Renewal of water	Microbiological control of water Control of cleaning and disinfection programs Blanching max time: 5 min opt. temperature: T=73°C
9. PARTIAL DRYING OF SLICES BEFORE DEEP FRYING	MICROBIOLOGICAL Microorganism from equipment, environment (potato slices remain for a short time before frying) PHYSICAL Foreign materials	GMP - GHP Assurance of hygienic conditions Protection the product from the environment Cleaning and disinfection of equipment Personnel training	Control of cleaning and disinfection programs Control of environment hygiene Max removal of moisture: 4% Draw away of foreign material
10. DEEP FRYING	MICROBIOLOGICAL The majority of microorganisms are destroyed CHEMICAL Residues of cleaning agents and lubricant Oxidation and polymerization products of oil PHYSICAL Foreign materials Contamination of fresh oil/fat with used oil/fat	GMP - GHP Assurance of hygienic conditions Cleaning and disinfection of equipment Antifoam and antioxidants and their percent in oil/fat approved for foods Use lubricant and cleaning agents approved for foods Personnel training Maintenance of equipment	Temperature: 165-185°C (opt. T: 177°C) Turn over time of oil/fat 5-10 h Control of correct use of antifoams and antioxidants Replace oil/fat according to specifications (country's legislation) Max consumption of trans fatty acid: 2.7-12.8 g/day Max consume of acrylamide: 0.5 mg/Kg Control for foreign materials

stage	Hazards/reason	Preventative measures	Critical factors/limits/controls
10a. PREFRYING, FREEZING & PACKAGING	<u>MICROBIOLOGICAL</u> Microorganism from air, equipment, personnel (the product should be cooked by consumers) <u>CHEMICAL</u> Residues of cleaning agents <u>PHYSICAL</u> Foreign materials	Packaging material approved for foods Suppliers of packaging material (SQA) Maintenance of freezer Protect the product from the environment	T: -20 °C for 7-12 min (unpacked) T: -20 °C for 3-7h (packed in paper boxes) Control of freezing rate Control of cleaning and disinfection programs Control for foreign materials Check for correct closing of the package
11. REMOVAL OF EXTRA (NOT WANTED) QUANTITY OF OIL/FAT	<u>MICROBIOLOGICAL</u> Contamination (air, equipment, surfaces, personnel) <u>CHEMICAL</u> Residues of cleaning agents <u>PHYSICAL</u> Foreign materials	GMP - GHP Assurance of hygienic conditions Cleaning and disinfection of equipment and surfaces Personnel training	Control of cleaning and disinfection programs Microbiological control of equipment and surfaces Control for foreign materials
12. SALTING CHIPS & ADDING FLAVORING MATERIALS	<u>MICROBIOLOGICAL</u> Contamination (air, equipment, personnel) <u>CHEMICAL</u> Residues of chemicals in the materials <u>PHYSICAL</u> Foreign materials	GMP - GHP Assurance of hygienic conditions Cleaning and disinfection of equipment Hygiene handling of materials Maintenance of equipment Personnel training	Control of cleaning and disinfection programs Control for foreign materials Inspection of material handling by the personnel

Stage	Hazards/reasons	Preventative measures	Critical factors/limits/controls
13. INSPECTION & COOLING	<u>MICROBIOLOGICAL</u> Contamination (air, equipment, personnel) (the final product remains for a short time for cooling before its packaging) <u>PHYSICAL</u> Foreign materials	GMP - GHP Protection the product from the environment Assurance of hygienic conditions Cleaning and disinfection of equipment Ventilation for good cooling Personnel training	Control of cleaning and disinfection programs Control for foreign materials and draw away Control for chips with defects or undesirable characteristics and direct reject Control of hygiene in the environment during cooling
14. PACKAGING	<u>MICROBIOLOGICAL</u> Contamination (air, equipment, personnel, packaging material) <u>CHEMICAL</u> Contaminants from the packaging materials <u>PHYSICAL</u> Foreign materials	Suppliers of packaging material (SQA) Packaging material approved for foods Protection of the packaging area away from the production area Metal detector after packaging Coding of product	Check the specifications of packaging materials Control for foreign materials Check for the correct closing of the package Check for the correct coding Removal of products with defects Control of cleaning and disinfection programs Control of metal detector
15. STORAGE OF FINISHED PRODUCT	<u>MICROBIOLOGICAL</u> Contamination (moisture, pests) in case of not correctly closed packaged products <u>CHEMICAL</u> Residues of chemicals and pesticides in case of not correctly closed packaged products	GMP - GHP Assurance of hygienic conditions in storage area Control of cleaning and disinfection programs Pests control programs Hygiene storage of final products	Control of programs: cleaning and disinfection, pest control Control of hygiene in storage area Control for foreign materials Check for the correct closing of the package

Table 8 HACCP flowsheet for potato chips and Fries

CCPs:

- Metal detection – metal detector machine
- Moisture content below 4%

Product description and intended use according to HACCP

Item	Product Description
Product description	Tetos by CBL is a potato snack made using real potato.
Physical properties	Product should be free from rancidity, undesirable odor and color
Chemical characteristics	Moisture (3%), Oil (40%), salt before seasoning (3%), Ash (4%) and Free fatty acid (FFA) (1.5%) as oleic oil.
Microbiological characteristics	Product should be free from microorganisms and pathogenic microbes which causing poisoning and their toxin, bacteria count 50000 cfu, Bacillus count maximum 10000 cfu.
Nutritional value Serving size 20g	Energy 92.00 kcal Protein 1.20g Carbohydrates 13.30g • Of which sugar 0.88g •Dietary fiber 0.90g Total fat 4.26g • Saturated fat 1.90g • Mono unsaturated fat 1.60g • Poly unsaturated fat 0.40g •Trans fat 0.00g Sodium 0.24g
Storage conditions	Store in cool and dry place away from insects
Distribution methods	Supermarkets, retails
Shelf life	1 year
Consumer requirements	Ready for consumption for all ages, direct consumption

Table 9 Product description and intended use of CBL Tetos according to HACCP

Allowed composition of the product

Characteristic	Requirement
Moisture, per cent by mass, max	6.0
Fat (on dry basis), per cent by mass, max	25
Peroxide value, mill equivalents oxygen/kg fat, max	10
Acid insoluble ash (on dry basis), per cent by mass, max	0.1

Table 10 Composition of CBL Tetos

Microbial limits allowed

Test	Limit	Method of test
Aerobic plate count, per g, max	1 x 10 ⁴	SLS 516 : Part 1
Coliform, per g, max	10	SLS 516 : Part 3
E.coli	Absent in 1 g	SLS 516 : Part 3
Salmonella	Absent in 25 g	SLS 516 : Part 5

Table 11 Microbiological limits allowed for CBL Tetos (SLS 516)

CBL Potato Crackers

Product description and intended use according to HACCP

Item	Product Description
Product description	popular snacks prepared with a combination of wheat and potato
Physical properties	Product should be free from undesirable odor and color
Chemical characteristics	Moisture (3%), Oil (40%), salt before seasoning (3%), Ash (4%) and Free fatty acid (FFA) (1.5%) as oleic oil.
Microbiological characteristics	Product should be free from microorganisms and pathogenic microbes which causing poisoning and their toxin, bacteria count 50000 cfu, Bacillus count maximum 10000 cfu.
Nutritional value Serving size 28g	Energy 122.78 kcal Protein 2.88 g Carbohydrates total 19.79g •Of which sugar 0.84g Dietary fibre 236.32 mg Total fat 3.56g • Saturated fat 1.54g
Storage conditions	Store in cool and dry place away from insects
Distribution methods	Supermarkets, retails
Shelf life	1 year
Consumer requirements	Ready for consumption for all ages, direct consumption

Table 12 Product description and intended use of CBL Potato Crackers according to HACCP

Microbial limits

Test Organism	N	c	Limit	
			m	M
Aerobic plate count	5	2	10 ³	10 ⁴
Yeast & mold count, per g	5	2	10 ²	10 ³
Coliforms, per g (MPN)	5	2	10	10 ²
E. coli, per g(MPN)	5	0	0	-
Staphylococcus aureus, per g	5	2	10	10 ²
Salmonella, per 25g	10	0	0	-

Table 13 Microbiological Requirement considered for CBL Potato crackers (SLS 251:210 biscuits)

Hazards, Control Measures, Monitoring and Corrective Actions of a Potato Processing Plant

	Hazards		Control measures	Target	Monitoring			Corrective actions
	Hazardous Agent(s)	Origin(s)			Activity	Responsibility	Records	
	Incoming Raw and Packaging Materials	Physical	Supplier	Reception criteria - Release of incoming material COC, COA, declaration (certification of compliance-analysis) Use of approved suppliers and audited	- No contamination coming from incoming material at supplier level	GMP inspection Internalaudit	QA head	GMP inspection records
Chemical								
Microbiological								

	Hazards		Control measures	Target	Monitoring		Corrective actions
	Hazardous Agent(s)	Origin(s)			Activity	Records	
Raw and Packaging Materials (Stored)	Physical contamination by damaged parts of the packaging	Mishandling	Inspection, release of incoming raw and packaging material Following of good hygienic storage practices.	Absence of foreign bodies due to non-conform packaging.	GMP inspection Internalaudit	GMP inspection records Internalaudit report	Reject damaged packaging material Retrain Review release procedure
	Microbiological contamination	Operators, storage conditions (pest contamination).		All staff are aware of hygienic issues and comply with good working practices when manipulating packaging's.			
	Chemical contamination	Migration of Raw material in the product	Only food grade materials are used for packaging				

	Hazards		Control measures	Target			Corrective actions
	Hazardous Agent(s)	Origin(s)			Activity	Records	
waste	Physical	Incorrect Waste disposal	Waste are identified,	Waste does not represent	GMP audit	GMP inspection records	Re identify wastecontainer, make the responsibility of disposed of clear, change damaged waste container
		Chemical Waste not	collected and disposed of.	avector of physical,			
	Chemical	properly stored	Packaging waste are	attraction for pest activity,			
		disposed-of	grinding and disposed of	microbiological and			
	Microbiological	Waste not properly	Waste container are	chemical contamination			
		stored	closable				

	Hazards		Control measures	Target			Corrective actions
	Hazardous Agent(s)	Origin(s)			Activity	Records	
Calibration	Chemical	over / under dosage of ingredients	verification, calibration activities on equipment used to monitor, produce, store product for consumption	Device for measure areworking properly	GMP audit	GMP inspection record	- Review verification andcalibration plan, apply verification and calibration on device for measuring
	Microbiological	Product parameters monitored with a non- compliant device					

	Hazards		Control measures	Target			Corrective actions
	Hazardous Agent(s)	Origin(s)			Activity	Records	
	Storage	Physical	product not properly closed, non integrity of packaging raw materials	Control of temp in raw material, finished product storage area - Monitoring of ambient air - FiFo is observed - Only electric forklift is used - cleaning activities in storage area - chemical and lubricant are stored separately	Storage of raw materials, equipment, and lubricants does not represent a vector of chemical, microbiological and physical contaminations for finished product	GMP audit hygiene monitoring	GMP inspection records
	Chemical	Storage of chemicals- environmental					
	Microbiological	Humidity, temperature of environment	segregated non conform material - training of operator- Zoning rules				

	Hazards		Control Measures	Target			Corrective Actions
	Hazardous Agent(s)	Origin(s)			Activity	Records	
Control of personnel	Physical contamination by foreign bodies (jewelry, hair, clothes etc)	The personnel and its belongings	Implementation of hygienic personal practices. Full training on food safety and good hygienic practices. Respect of the zoning plan and the restriction linked to each area (jewelry forbidden in green zone).	Absence of foreign bodies due to personnel belongings	GMP inspection	GMP inspection records	Retraining Disciplinary action
	Microbiological contamination due to insufficient hygiene (dirty hands, illness (sneezing-coughing- fever), outdoor clothes, etc)	The personnel and its clothes	Temporary exclusion from production site of ill staff members. Enough Washing and disinfection tools are provided.	All staff is aware of hygienic issues and comply with good manufacturing practices.			

	Hazards		Control Measures	Target	Monitoring		Corrective Actions
	Hazardous Agent(s)	Origin(s)			Activity	Records	
Pest Control	Physical and microbiological contamination brought by pests (hair, excrement, body parts, bacteria, molds etc.)	Pests (Insects, rodents, birds etc...)	Use of pest control devices and chemicals only by fully trained operators. Use of approved authorized chemicals and devices fitted for food company.	Absence of foreign bodies and microbiological contaminations due to pests presence.	GMP inspection record	GMP inspection records	Notification of the company which provide service and Frequent assessment of it
	Chemical and physical contamination by pest control devices (baits, traps, insecticides, spraying etc..)	Misuse or storage of chemicals and poor management of devices used for pest control.	Correct placement of control units. No toxic baits inside the production area.	No contamination by pests control measures.	GMP inspection	GMP Inspection record	
	Microbiological	humidity, temperature environment	Clean and dry work areas.				

	Hazards		Control Measures	Target	Monitoring		Corrective Actions
	Hazardous Agent(s)	Origin(s)			Activity	Records	
Maintenance of equipment	Physical contamination by loose equipment parts, forgotten tools, etc.	Poorly maintained equipment, technician's bad maintaining habits or mistakes.	Maintenance by trained and experienced operators. Only food-contact grade materials are used e.g. food grade lubricant.	Absence of foreign bodies due to poor maintenance.			Review maintenance plan Retrain
	Microbiological contamination of parts in contact with food during maintenance.	bad habits, mistakes technician's during maintenance or insufficient cleaning.	Cleaning and verification after maintenance.	Avoiding microbiological contamination due to maintenance.	GMP inspection (maintenance plan inspection)	GMP inspection records	
	Chemical contamination due to use of inappropriate material for maintenance, e.g. use of nonfood contact grade lubricant	Technician's bad maintaining habits or mistakes.		Use the right products and protocols for equipment maintenance.			

Table 14 Hazards, Control Measures, Monitoring and Corrective Actions of a Potato Processing Plant

2.2 Production & Quality Assurance of Processed Potato Products available in Sri Lanka

2.2.1 Imported French Fries

Introduction

A popular and common culinary treat, French fries go through a rigorous production process to guarantee the highest standards of flavor and quality. The key to this procedure is the careful selection of the *Russet burbank* potato type, which is well-known for its outstanding processing and baking capabilities. A key component in the endeavor to produce the best French fries is the selection of the *Russet burbank* potato cultivar. Its superior baking qualities help it achieve the desired taste and texture that customers are looking for. Additionally, this variety's easy processing properties simplify the production process and guarantee consistency in the finished product.

Beyond the potato fields, to the companies charged with supplying the raw materials, there is a commitment to quality. Only suppliers that have gained international acceptance are taken into account, and the supply quality control procedure thoroughly audits them to guarantee that they conform to strict requirements. This rigorous selection procedure ensures that the raw materials fulfill the most stringent industry standards, paving the way for the manufacturing of high-quality French fries.

When storing these carefully chosen raw materials, temperature becomes an important control point. Since maintaining ideal conditions can prevent French fries from becoming brittle, the production process places a high priority on doing so. In order to protect the integrity and quality of the potatoes, raw potato products are shipped in freezers. The potatoes will always be in the best possible condition, prepared for the next steps of production, thanks to this proactive approach to temperature regulation. French fries that are imported are stored with even more attention to temperature control. Until they are ready to go through the production process, these frozen treats are kept at temperatures below -15 °C in storage. This freezing technique maintains the freshness of the imported fries while also fostering an atmosphere that sustains their superior quality.

A visual indication highlights the dedication to quality and hygiene throughout the whole production process. Blue gloves are worn by those who handle raw materials, signifying a distinct division between the handling of raw and cooked goods. Maintaining the highest hygiene standards and preventing cross-contamination depend heavily on this procedure. Conversely, the management of cooked goods is left to those donning white gloves, underscoring the rigid division between the two phases.

For French fries, the process from field to table is a meticulously planned symphony of quality controls. The *Russet burbank* potato type is chosen, internationally recognized suppliers are inspected, temperature control is prioritized, and colored gloves serve as visual clues. All of these factors work together to produce French fries that constantly meet and surpass consumer expectations. Because of this dedication to quality, every serving of French fries is guaranteed to be more than just a snack—rather, it is a carefully and precisely prepared gourmet experience.

Process Line

Receiving imported French fries:

French fries imported from overseas are the first product of the manufacturing process. This entails the inbound shipment being carefully unloaded and inspected. To maintain their freshness and quality throughout transit, the imported fries are sent frozen.

Quality Inspection:

After shipment, a comprehensive inspection for quality is conducted. This phase entails evaluating the imported French fries' overall condition, temperature, and look. Any departures from the set standards of quality are

immediately identified and dealt with. Through this examination, it is made sure that only superior raw materials move on to the next phases of the production process.

Cold Storage:

Once the French fries have undergone quality control, they are kept in refrigerated storage facilities. The fries are kept frozen in these facilities until they are ready to go through the production process since the temperature is kept below -15 °C. In order to maintain the raw materials' quality and freshness and prevent any possible deterioration before processing, cold storage is an essential step.

Processing Area:

The conversion of raw ingredients into finished French fries takes place in the processing section. The equipment and supplies needed for frying and packaging fries are located in this area. This is probably where the *Russet burbank* potatoes, prized for their superior baking and processing abilities, are produced. The production crew makes sure that safety and hygienic requirements are upheld at all times, wearing blue gloves when handling raw materials.

The French fries go through one last check after processing to make sure they live up to the required standards of quality. Taste, texture, size, and color inspections may be part of this examination. To ensure that the finished product is of the highest caliber, any fries that do not fit the requirements are discarded.

Requirements:

Characteristics		Specification
String Length	% of ≥ 3"	30% min. (per # of sticks)
	% of ≥ 3-2"	70% min. (per # of sticks)
	Slivers & Shorts (<2")	2% max. (per # of sticks)
Presence of Black/Grey/Green Pieces/ Spots		5 pcs/500g max.
Presence of Impurities/ any Foreign Matters		Nil
Temperature Condition		Frozen (-18°C)
Shelf Life		1 1/2 Years
Sensory Parameters	Surface Color	Crispy to Bite, Not Crunchy
	Outer Texture	Light Resistance to Bite
	Inner Texture	Typical French Fries Aroma
	Aroma	Typical French Fries Flavor
	Flavor	Typical French Fries Flavor

Table 15 Quality inspection requirements

Inspection based on length of the French fries:

Figure 13 Quality grades of French fries according to the length

Figure 14 Quality defects of French fries

Microbiological Requirements:

Microbiological tests (cfu/gm)	Processing line	Result before frying	Result after frying	Specification
Total plate count	1	3.6×10^{6a}	10×10^b	≤ 50000
	2	2.7×10^{6b}	7×10^c	
Mold & yeast	1	9.0×10^{5c}	1×10^d	≤ 500
	2	6.6×10^{5d}	20×10^a	
Staphylococcus aureus	1	Nil ^h	Nil ^e	Nil
	2	Nil ^h	Nil ^e	
Bacillus cereus	1	3.2×10^{3e}	Nil ^e	≤ 10000
	2	5.2×10^{2f}	Nil ^e	
E. Coli	1	1.2×10^{2g}	Nil ^e	≤ 10
	2	2.7×10^{2g}	Nil ^e	

*cfu/1gm = colony forming unit / gm.
 *The limits are according (E.S: 1629:2017).
 Values followed by different letter in columns are significantly different at p <0.05.

Table 16 : Microbiological analysis of potato slices before and after frying for two processing lines

Testing for French fries

External laboratory testing:

Representative manufacturing samples are subjected to rigorous testing at external labs like Bureau Veritas or SGS once every two weeks. This regularity guarantees that the product is evaluated in a methodical and reliable manner.

A series of tests are carried out by the external laboratories to evaluate a number of factors, such as nutritional value, regulatory compliance, and microbiological safety. These tests offer a neutral and objective assessment of the general quality and safety of the product.

Sensory testing:

An organoleptic panel specifically used in the plant is used to subjectively evaluate the French fry's organoleptic qualities. The fries' creamy, white color, opacity, and smoothness are among the visual attributes that the sensory panel assesses. The fries' mouthfeel and texture are evaluated, with particular attention paid to characteristics like thickness, smoothness, and creaminess, as well as how well they clear up in the mouth overall. The sensory panel assesses the fries' flavor and odor, aiming for a slightly sweet, creamy dairy combination with a noticeable vanilla taste.

Oil quality assessment:

The total quality of the French fries depends greatly on the quality of the frying oil. Diatomaceous earth and activated carbon are used to evaluate the quality of oil. These substances work as filters for the oil, drawing out contaminants and absorbing color. The oil's hue serves as a visual indication as to its quality. An indicator of the oil's stability when frying at high temperatures is its smoke point, which is measured. Free fatty acids are important to track, but because titration takes time, measurements of these substances are not made often. This technique, which measures the oil's acidity, should only be used for recurring, comprehensive evaluations.

2.2.2 Potato Chips

Introduction

When making potato chips, selecting potatoes as the main ingredient is crucial. The particular type that is imported from Sri Lanka is probably chosen according to its starch content, composition, and frying ability. The final product's texture, color, and flavor are greatly influenced by the makeup of the potatoes. The flavor and texture of potato chips are greatly influenced by the type of oil that is used. The selection of locally provided oil is probably influenced by factors such as stability, appropriateness for high-temperature frying, and overall effect on chip sensory qualities. Oil is used as a cooking medium and as a vehicle for seasonings.

The decision to import seasoning powder implies a concentration on reaching particular sensory attributes and flavor profiles. To ensure that the potato chips have a unique and enticing flavor, the imported seasoning powder is probably chosen for its special combination of spices, herbs, and other flavoring ingredients. There are several scientific justifications for using nitrogen gas in the manufacturing of potato chips. An inert gas called nitrogen aids in establishing a regulated environment inside the package. By preventing oxidation, this regulated climate keeps the chips fresher longer on the shelf. Nitrogen gas can also assist maintain the crispness of the chips while giving them the right texture.

Reasons for not using local potato varieties;

The choice to use imported potatoes could have its origins in the scientific difficulties native varieties provide during frying. Different potato varieties fry differently due to differences in moisture and starch content. It's possible that imported potatoes have a more stable composition, which would produce better and more consistent frying results. One logistical problem for the production process is the restricted availability of local potato types. Maintaining the finished product's quality and attributes requires a consistent supply of raw materials. More dependable sources for imported potatoes could result in a steady and predictable supply chain.

Crop yields, storage limitations, and seasonal fluctuations can all contribute to the challenge of keeping a steady supply of local potato varieties. Sri Lankan potatoes can be imported, which improves the supply chain's stability and uniformity and raises manufacturing efficiency and consistency.

Process Line

Receiving fresh potatoes:

- When you receive fresh potatoes, it's important to check for external quality characteristics including consistency in size, hardness, and lack of bruises. Any harmed or inferior potatoes have the potential to lower the overall quality of the chips.
- Fresh potato storage and shipping involve potential contamination hazards. To ensure the safety of the raw material, appropriate procedures like safe handling, hygienic conditions, and pest control should be put in place.

Cleaning and sorting:

- To ensure a high-quality end output, all leftover defective or off-spec chips are removed using thorough cleaning and sorting procedures.
- There is a chance of cross-contamination when sorting. For safety, it is imperative to separate the various chip grades and practice good hygiene.

Washing:

- Achieving a clean appearance and avoiding uneven frying of the chips is made possible by the efficient removal of debris and leftover starch by washing.
- To prevent contaminating the water used for washing, the quality of the water is essential. Maintaining food safety regulations requires the use of proper sanitation techniques.

Peeling and slicing:

- Consistency in chip thickness and texture is mostly dependent on uniform peeling and slicing. Inconsistencies in these procedures may result in unequal cooking and low-quality output.
- Equipment used for peeling and slicing must be properly maintained and cleaned in order to avoid cross-contamination and guarantee product safety.

Blanching, Centrifugal and Dewatering or oiling:

- It's crucial to blanch and de-oil the chips properly to get rid of extra oil so the chips don't get too greasy and yet have an appealing texture. Enzymes must be deactivated and the color and texture of the chips

must be preserved through proper blanching. Inappropriate blanching might produce chips that aren't the right color and have lost some of their flavor and texture.

- Contaminants might be introduced by the water used for blanching. To guarantee product safety, appropriate water quality management and sanitation practices are required.
- Sufficient de-oiling avoids oil traces that could lead to a greasy mouthfeel. Moreover, it lessens the possibility of oil oxidation, which can lead to unwanted flavors and affect safety.

Hot air drying:

- To get the appropriate crispiness in the finished product and to eliminate surface moisture, effective hot air drying is essential. Uneven frying and a less-than-ideal texture can result from incomplete drying.
- It's essential to keep drying equipment clean and well-maintained to stop the growth of mold or bacteria.

Frying:

- To get the right texture and color, the frying temperature must be carefully watched and maintained. Off-flavors and excessive oil absorption might result from overheating.
- It is crucial to maintain the frying oil's stability and cleanliness in order to stop dangerous chemicals from forming. For the sake of quality and safety, regular oil replacement and filtration are essential.

Inspection:

- Extensive examination at several phases guarantees the elimination of faulty or substandard potatoes. Regular quality inspections aid in preserving consistency in the finished product.
- To avoid any contamination throughout the inspection process, inspection staff members should adhere to hygiene protocols.

Blast freezing and packaging:

- It is essential to freeze potatoes quickly in order to maintain their original texture. When something is frozen incorrectly, it might cause damage to the cells, which makes it mushy or soggy when it thaws.
- To prevent contamination, packaging materials must adhere to food safety regulations. In order to avoid microbiological growth during storage and transit, packaging hygiene is essential.

Cold Storage:

- Potatoes must be kept in a constant cold storage condition to avoid sprouting, rotting, and texture loss. Variations in temperature can have an effect on the quality by encouraging the production of sugar, which can change the flavor and color during later stages of processing.
- There is a risk of cross-contamination in shared cold storage facilities. To avoid toxins from becoming transferred to potatoes that are being stored, adequate separation and hygiene procedures are required.

Quality inspection procedure for raw materials

POTATO

- Check the variety of the potato.
- Check the moisture level of the potato.
- Check for the suitable packaging materials used for potatoes because, based on the packing method, it determines the amount of potato waste and the quality of the final product.

- Check whether the potato supplier is a GMP-certified farmer or not in order to reduce the impact of pesticide residue on the final product.

OIL

- An oil supplier should have ISO, BRCGS, and FSSC quality certifications in order to be accepted as an approved supplier.
- By using an oil tester, check the polar matter content in the oil. The normal TPM [total polar matter] value should be between 5 and 7%.
- The colour of the oil, the odour of the oil, and the foreign matter content are also checked in the oil inspection procedure.

SEASONING POWDER

- Check for the packaging material of the seasoning powder, color, odor, taste, moisture content, and particle size of the powder.
- Normally, moisture content should be below 5%.

Problems arise during potato chip production

A complex chemical interaction involving amino acids and reducing sugars is known as the Maillard reaction, which gives potato chips their widely recognized light brown hue. On the other hand, the dark color that appears when frying raises the risk of overbrowning from extended heat exposure. This can cause unwanted substances to develop, such as acrylamide, which could add to the dark coloring. According to science, regulating elements like oil quality, temperature, and frying time can aid in preserving the intended light brown hue.

There are a number of reasons why potato chips can develop a bitter taste. First of all, when the potatoes are picked matters; those that are harvested later in the season could have higher concentrations of certain chemicals, which adds to the bitterness. Furthermore, the type of potato used and its natural chemical makeup—especially its sugar content—can affect how bitter aromas emerge when fried. From a scientific standpoint, it is imperative to comprehend and regulate these variables in order to consistently attain the intended flavor profile.

Critical control points:

- The total polar materials (TPM) of frying oil serve as a quality indicator. When oil is fried, it is exposed to high temperatures that cause chemical changes. Degradation is indicated by the accumulation of polar molecules. A TPM level of less than 24% is a crucial control point to make sure the oil stays within permissible bounds, avoiding the emergence of off tastes, and preserving the chips' intended sensory qualities.
- The temperature and length of the frying process have a major role in controlling the Maillard reaction and chip texture. The ideal temperature range of 165–175°C and cooking time of 2.45–3.45 minutes are chosen to provide the right amount of crispiness and light brown hue. These settings are precisely regulated, according to science, to balance the Maillard process without causing over-browning or unfavorable texture changes.
- A crucial control point for guaranteeing the end product's quality and safety is metal detection. Metallic impurities have the potential to damage product integrity and safety. According to science, undesired metallic particles are identified and removed by metal detecting systems using electromagnetic principles, thereby averting potential risks and guaranteeing customer safety.

Quality and Safety control measures for potato chip production process

Microbial contamination is one type of biological hazard that might compromise product safety. A strong quality control system is in place for raw material inspections in order to reduce this risk. Scientific techniques, such as

microbiological analysis, can be used to make sure that the entering raw materials are free of dangerous microorganisms.

There are several uses for high-temperature frying of potato chips. It successfully lowers the potatoes' water content, improving their crispness. Furthermore, frying at high temperatures helps to destroy germs that could be dangerous, guaranteeing the safety of the finished product.

Physical hazards, such as foreign objects or contaminants, are mitigated through thorough inspection of raw materials. Scientific techniques, including visual inspection and technological tools like metal detectors, are employed to identify and eliminate any physical hazards that may compromise the safety and quality of the final product.

Standards and regulations related manufacturing of potato chips:

An international standard called ISO 22000:2018 describes the specifications needed for a food safety management system. Scientific concepts are integrated to guarantee the management of food safety risks during the entire production process. This covers methodical techniques for risk assessment and hazard analysis.

GMP regulations give industrial operations a solid scientific basis to guarantee uniformity, security, and quality. These recommendations address a number of topics, such as staff procedures, equipment upkeep, and facility cleanliness, all of which support the scientific basis of safe and high-quality food production.

A methodical strategy to detecting, assessing, and managing risks to food safety is called HACCP. It is grounded in science and follows a set of guidelines that highlight the crucial stages of the production process where risks can be avoided, minimized, or brought down to manageable levels.

A framework for food safety and quality management systems is provided by BRCGS. It adheres to scientific principles and is predicated on risk assessment and preventive measures to guarantee that products fulfill strict safety and quality requirements.

2.2.3 Local Frozen French Fries

CLD Farm Fresh Pvt Ltd, which is in Bandarawela, is Sri Lanka's first Frozen French Fries manufacturing plant. For production the company uses improved granola variety through a collaboration with the Industrial Technology Institute (ITI), This variety ensures that the fries get the required crispiness and required color after frying. The company employs "zero balance stock" approach, to avoid wastage and post-harvest losses. The company has acquired HACCP certification.

Process Line

Figure 7 Process line for Local frozen French fries production

Quality and Safety Issues in Process Line

The production line faces quality and safety concerns, primarily attributed to several factors. These include,

- Wastage due to the use of small-sized potatoes
- Soil weight accompanying potato purchases
- Contamination risks from damaged potatoes, microorganisms, and foreign materials.
- Uneven potato thickness, improper cutting, inconsistent sizes, and inadequate peeling, leading to the loss of potato flesh
- Insufficient blanching or overcooking
- Uneven frying, freezer burns, and fluctuating temperatures.

Process and preventive measures of Process Line

Receiving Fresh Potatoes

The company exclusively buy from farmers who practice good farming/agricultural practices, registered in their database. At the unloading area, thorough inspections are conducted, focusing on size, weight, cleanliness and transportation quality. This process takes place in a clean and controlled receiving environment.

Cleaning and Sorting

Manual removal of soil and foreign materials using a sorting conveyor manned by trained staff. Potatoes are sorted based on size. The minimum diameter should be 75mm and this step is a critical control point. Potatoes are also sorted on appearance, and damage to minimize waste. Small potatoes are allocated for the market, larger ones for the French fries' factory and SL catering. Damaged or green-colored potatoes are removed after physical inspection.

Figure 8 Sorting of potatoes

Washing and Peeling

The washing and peeling phase utilizes high-pressure water sprayers and bubble washers with driers, incorporating chlorine and "Vege wash" in the water mixture. Water samples are regularly checked. Abrasive peeling machines/ washing machines effectively remove the peel before slicing.

Slicing

Slicing is done by a French fries cutter to get accurate and precise cut sizes to maintain quality and market value. Blade sharpness is regularly monitored.

Blanching and Centrifugal De-watering

Blanching is done in blanching machines using hot water at temperatures between 60-80 °C for 5-8 minutes. This is a critical control point. Then centrifugal de-watering machines are used to remove excess water ensuring proper drainage.

Hot air drying

Air cooling/drying systems with conveyor belts are used to dry, maintaining a temperature of 175°C for 5-20 minutes, ensuring quality and safety. This is also a critical control point.

Frying

Frying is done using continuous fryers with oil heating systems, emphasizing consistent oil temperature control between 150-170°C for 15-60 seconds, with a turnover time of 5 hours as a critical control point.

Centrifugal De-oiling

Post-frying, centrifugal de-oiling machines remove excess oil while ensuring proper drainage.

Inspection

Inspection is done on inspection tables. Conveyor sorting is done, and inspection mainly involves visual inspection. Size sorting is done to sort three size defects as silver, small pieces and scraps. Scraps are not allowed in products. Maximum 12% of silvers and maximum 6% of scraps are allowed in product.

Through inspection frying defects are identified. Those are burnt pieces which are dark brown in color. Visuals defects are classified as minor, major and serious, those are dependent on cross section.

Blast Freezing and Packaging

B last freezing is done blast freezers set between -30 to -35°C for 30-50 minutes per batch, ensuring frozen fries without internal holes. This is a critical control point. Packaging materials are outsourced.

Table 17 Quality and Safety Parameters used for Local frozen French fries

Product description	Fresh potato slices 7mm cross section, no flavors added, Vegetable oil, Salt
Physical Properties	Product should be free from rancidity, undesirable odor and slices color ≥55L
Chemical Characteristics	Moisture (3%), Oil (40%), salt before seasoning (3%), Ash (4%) and Free fatty acid (FFA) (1.5%) as oleic oil.
Microbiologic al Characteristics	Product should be free from microorganisms and pathogenic microbes which causing poisoning and their toxin, bacteria count 50000 cfu, Bacillus count maximum 10000 cfu.
Nutritional Value	Calories 157
Serving size 100g	Total fat 3g, 45% Daily value Sodium 236 mg, 10% Total carbohydrates 29g, 39% Protein 4g Salt 0.6g Sugar <0.25g

Storage conditions	Store -18°C or below and away from sunlight
Distribution methods	Supermarkets, restaurants, retails, malls and hotels
Shelf life	6 months
Consumer requirements	Ready for consumption for all ages, direct consumption, take the product out of the freezer and keep for about 2-3 minutes, deep fry the frozen French fries at 175-180°C hot oil for 5-6 minutes , do not refreeze after thawing

Cold Storage

Packaged frozen French fries are stored in a freezer at -18°C or below with temperature control. This is a critical control point. Packages are evenly distributed in the freezer

2.2.4 CBL Tetos

As ingredients Potato flakes, Wheat flour, Corn grits, Palm olein, Sugar, Salt, Vitamin, Minerals, Permitted antioxidants and flavors are used by Ceylon Biscuit Limited.

Tetos is an extruded potato snack produced from real potato flakes. The potato flakes used by the company are imported from certified suppliers.

Process Line

3. Potential Hazards of Potato Products

The potential health hazards commonly noted with Potato products are Trans fatty acids, Acrylamide, Polymerized products, Hydrolyzed products. The most serious consequences for human health are coronary illness and cardiologic diseases.

Acrylamide

- Found in foods especially in fried potato chips and in all products which contain starch and are fried, heated or cooked in temperatures higher than 171°C.
- Acrylamide is considered to provoke carcinogenesis.
- The only recognized effect of acrylamide in the human organism is that it can induce **toxic effects** in the nervous system.
- Many experiments have shown that the maximum quantity that can be consumed without problems is **0.5 mg/Kg**.

Trans-Fatty acids

- **Trans fatty acids** are produced during hydrogenation.

Polymerized Products

As oil and fats undergo heating in the deep- frying process, various decomposition products are formed. Some of these products are volatile at frying temperature.

Such volatile products are:

- Peroxides
- Aldehydes
- Monoglycerides

The non-volatile decomposition products include polar compounds resulting in gumming and foaming.

Such non-volatile products are:

- Monomers
- Dimers
- Trimers
- Other High-molecular-weight Compounds Both of the above are undesirable in the frying process.

Hydrolyzed products

The rate of hydrolysis or free fatty acid development depends on the following factors:

- **Amount of water** released into the frying fat
- **Frying temperature** (the higher the temperature, the more rapid the rate of free fatty acid production).

- **Fat turnover rate** (the more rapid the replacement of used oil/fat with fresh, the slower the rate of free fatty acid development).

Figure 32 Analysis of Acrylamide

Potato allergy, though relatively uncommon compared to other food allergies, can elicit serious and potentially life-threatening reactions in sensitive individuals both adults and children. While the allergy primarily stems from proteins found in potatoes, such as patatine, which are often associated with the tuber's peel, the presence of solanine adds an additional layer of complexity. Solanine, a natural toxin produced by potatoes, is typically concentrated in the peel and green parts of the potato. Understanding the nuances of potato allergy involves recognizing the role of patatine, a protein that can trigger immune responses, and being aware of the potential dangers associated with solanine, which can pose health risks if consumed in large quantities. Immune system 'mistakes' patatine within the potato as harmful substances and responds defensively. This exploration delves into the intricacies of potato allergy, shedding light on the allergenic components like patatine and the safety concerns surrounding solanine, aiming to foster a greater understanding of this condition and promote informed dietary choices.

Solanine

Solanine is a toxic alkaloid that is semi poisonous. With the exception of 'green potatoes' (which contain higher levels of this toxin), solanine is generally safe to eat in moderation when consuming potatoes and other agricultural nightshades. While true solanine allergies are rare, some individuals may experience adverse reactions or sensitivities to solanine, a natural toxin found in potatoes and other members of the nightshade family, such as tomatoes and eggplants. Solanine is most concentrated in the peel and green parts of potatoes, and its levels can increase when potatoes are exposed to light. Symptoms of solanine toxicity may include gastrointestinal issues like nausea, vomiting, and stomach cramps, as well as neurological symptoms like headache and dizziness. In severe cases, excessive consumption of solanine (green potatoes) can lead to more serious reactions, including difficulty breathing and in extreme cases, coma. Some individuals are unable to tolerate even small doses of solanine.

Solanine sensitivity is distinct from a true allergy as solanine poisoning can cause severe gastrointestinal issues and the immune system is not normally involved in the reaction. Allergic reactions involve the immune system, while solanine sensitivity typically results from the toxic nature of the compound. Individuals who suspect they may be sensitive to solanine should consult with a healthcare professional to determine the cause of their symptoms. To minimize solanine exposure, proper storage and preparation of potatoes, such as avoiding green or sprouted areas, can be crucial. As with any health concern, seeking medical advice is paramount for accurate diagnosis and appropriate management.

Patatine

Patatine is the major storage protein found in all potatoes, and it is more widely known as the primary contributor to potato allergies. It has been studied and identified as the major cause of potato allergy.

Symptoms: eczema, dermatitis, rashes, hives, and other skin conditions

4. Importation & Exportation of Potatoes

4.1 Local importation of potatoes

Imported potatoes play a significant role in Sri Lanka's food supply, offering consumers access to a diverse range of potato products and contributing to the country's food security. Sri Lanka imports potatoes from several countries to meet its domestic demand. The specific countries from which Sri Lanka imports potatoes may vary from year to year based on factors such as market conditions, trade agreements, and the availability of potatoes in different regions. Some of the countries that Sri Lanka commonly imports potatoes from include:

- Pakistan with a share of 73% (28 million US\$)
- Bangladesh with a share of 10.7% (4.18 million US\$)
- India with a share of 8.8% (3.43 million US\$)

- China with a share of 3.81% (1.48 million US\$)
- Netherlands with a share of 2.46% (963 thousand US\$)

Figure 9 Annual potato importation

However, ensuring consumer safety in the importation and consumption of potatoes is of paramount importance. Importing potatoes to Sri Lanka, like any agricultural import, can raise specific safety concerns related to the potential introduction of pests, diseases, and contaminants. To address these safety concerns, Sri Lanka's government typically implements strict regulations and inspection processes at its ports of entry. Importers are expected to comply with these regulations, and non-compliance can result in rejected shipments or other penalties.

It's crucial for importers, exporters, and regulatory authorities to work together to ensure the safe importation of potatoes and other agricultural products to protect both the country's agricultural sector and public health.

Here are some specific safety concerns associated with importing potatoes to Sri Lanka:

Phytosanitary Certificate: Potatoes imported into Sri Lanka should be accompanied by a phytosanitary certificate issued by the relevant plant health authority in the exporting country. This certificate confirms that the potatoes meet the phytosanitary standards of both the exporting and importing countries. This certificate attests that the potatoes meet Sri Lanka's phytosanitary standards and are free from pests and diseases.

Imported potatoes are subject to inspection and quarantine procedures at the point of entry into Sri Lanka. These procedures are in place to check for compliance with phytosanitary standards and other regulations.

In addition, there are guidelines for import of plants and plant products issued by National Plant Quarantine Service, Department of Agriculture and those guidelines are intended to facilitate plant and seed import, consistent with safety to crops in particular and the environment in general. In there, “seed potatoes” is mentioned as a form of plant material for import and potato is mentioned again as a restricted material to import from American tropics or any country in which South American Leaf Blight occurs.

Maximum Residue Limits (MRLs): Imported potatoes must comply with Sri Lanka's regulations regarding maximum residue limits (MRLs) for pesticides and chemical contaminants. Ensure that any chemicals used in the production and storage of potatoes are within permissible limits.

Food import control procedure is implemented at the borders by the Sri Lankan Food Control Administration Unit (FCAU) of Ministry of Health to ensure that the food arrives in Sri Lanka are safe for human consumption.

All imported food items should comply with the following regulations

- Food (labelling and advertising) Regulations 2011
- Food (shelf life for imported food items) Regulations 2012

The Food Control Administration Unit regulates the shelf life of imported food products. At the point of entry into Sri Lanka, the food should still have a **minimum of 60 percent** of its shelf life. The regulation states that the shelf life of an imported food is determined from the date-of-manufacture and the date-of expiry declared by the manufacturer. During this time, the product is considered safe for human consumption and of satisfactory quality in terms of nutritional value, flavor, texture, and appearance.

Import Food Inspection & Regulatory mechanism in Sri Lanka

Following is the regulatory mechanism adopted by the Food control unit, and in addition to this all food items arriving in the country should comply with the food (labelling and advertising) regulations 2005 and any other relevant regulations under the food Act No.26 of 1980.

For regulatory purposes all imported food items are categorized into 3 groups based on the perceived risk; and potato is categorized under the “Low Risk (Cereals, pulses, Fruits, Confectionery, primary agricultural products etc.)” category to take appropriate regulatory measures as follows;

<i>Prior permission</i>	<i>Documents required from the relevant authority in the exporting country</i>	<i>Conformity assessments</i>	<i>Parameters tested</i>	<i>Frequency of testing</i>
Not necessary	–	AEB analytical certificate chemical parameters	Radio activity Heavy metals Pesticide residues	Randomly

Table 18 Regulatory measures for potato importation to Sri Lanka

Packaging and Labeling: Potatoes should be packaged in accordance with Sri Lankan regulations. Packaging materials should be food-grade, and labeling should provide essential information, including the country of origin, production date, and any other required details.

Import Permits: Importers may need to obtain import permits from Import Permit Division, National Plant Quarantine Service, Katunayake, Sri Lanka. Obtaining a license for the importation of potatoes was mandatory prior to 1996. However, during mid-1996, the said policy was discontinued with the liberalization of importing of potatoes. Afterwards the government imposed a customs duty on import of potatoes, and the amount of duty was altered changed from time to time.

Customs Declarations: Accurate customs declarations, including the correct tariff codes and descriptions of the imported potatoes, are essential. Compliance with customs regulations is crucial to avoid delays and penalties.

Traceability: Establishing a traceability system to track the origin and movement of imported potatoes may be required to ensure transparency and facilitate recalls in case of safety concerns.

In conclusion, imported potatoes are a vital component of Sri Lanka's food supply, but ensuring consumer safety is a shared responsibility among government agencies, importers, and consumers themselves. By adhering to stringent quality and safety standards, implementing effective regulatory oversight, and promoting consumer awareness, Sri Lanka can enjoy the benefits of imported potatoes while minimizing potential health risks.

4.2 Exportation of potatoes

When considering exportation of potatoes, it is important to have a consistent supply of high- quality potatoes that meet the demands of foreign markets. This can be achieved by implementing good agricultural practices, such as proper fertilization, pest and disease management, and irrigation. It's also important to have a well-established distribution network and to be able to efficiently transport the potatoes to the port of export. Additionally, developing relationships with buyers and understanding their specific requirements can help to

secure profitable export deals. It's also important to be aware of and comply with any import regulations and tariffs that may be in place in the target market.

Top export destinations of "Potatoes, fresh or chilled" from Sri Lanka

- USA with a share of 41% (8.32 thousand US\$)
- Maldives with a share of 32% (6.55 thousand US\$)
- Qatar with a share of 23% (4.63 thousand US\$)
- United Arab Emirates with a share of 1.7% (342 US\$)
- Saudi Arabia – (170 US\$)

For spuds in their raw form, global sales for unprocessed potatoes exports by country amounted to US\$5.1 billion during 2022.

Beyond raw potatoes, the value of worldwide shipments for prepared or preserved potatoes including frozen French fries represents an additional \$11.1 billion in international sales.

The European Union, with its advanced agricultural infrastructure and vast production capacities, has established itself as a significant exporter of potatoes. Countries within the EU, such as the Netherlands and France, are known for their high-quality potato produce, making them preferred suppliers for many nations. Below are the 7 countries that exported the highest dollar value worth of unprocessed raw potatoes shipped during 2022.

- Netherlands: US\$964.5 million (18.8% of exported raw potatoes)
- France: \$849.2 million (16.5%)
- Germany: \$461.5 million (9%)
- Canada: \$427.9 million (8.3%)
- Egypt: \$316 million (6.2%)
- United States: \$303.7 million (5.9%)
- China: \$248.8 million (4.8%)

Frozen prepared or preserved potatoes including French fries amounted to \$8.1 billion in export sales for 2022 (thus equaling 72.8% of the overall prepared or preserved total), while international shipments of unfrozen prepared or preserved potatoes were worth another \$3 billion (representing 27.2%). Below are the 7 countries that exported the highest dollar value worth of prepared or preserved potatoes during 2022, including both frozen and unfrozen goods.

- Argentina: US\$2.23 billion (20.1% of exported frozen prepared/preserved potatoes)
- France: \$1.8 billion (16.7%)
- United States: \$1.51 billion (13.7%)
- Germany: \$1.46 billion (13.1%)
- Canada: \$559.3 million (5%)
- Belgium: \$535.2 million (4.8%)

- Netherlands: \$440.7 million (4%)

When exporting potatoes, there is no any specific regulation regarding the quality and safety of potatoes in local regulatory system other than the common legal aspects like business registration and other relevant procedures.

The regulatory aspects of potato exporting vary by country. Typically, exporters need to comply with the specifications mentioned by the importing destination and adhere to their demands regarding quality and safety concerns.

Potato export regulations are mentioned in the FAOLEX Database of Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. These Regulations lay down rules governing the exportation of potatoes and tubers as follows;

- Tubers intended for export must be sound, clean, whole and free from sprouts.
- The export of green, sunburnt or wrinkled tubers, or of tubers otherwise damaged is forbidden (reg. 3).
- Regulation 4 provides for the classification of potatoes for exports according to crops and according to shape, type and size.
- Regulations 7 to 11 concern packaging and containers. Every consignment of potatoes shall, before shipment, be subjected to inspection by an inspector of the Department of Agriculture.

5. Innovative Approaches Taken in Sri Lankan Potato Processing Industry

01. Improving the “Granola” variety

“Granola” is the local prevalent potato variety, but it was found to be not suitable for French Fries production as it alters the desired color and crispiness of French Fries.

As a solution, a local small-scale company in collaboration with Industrial Technology Institute (ITI) has improved the typical Granola variety to be used by the local industry to produce French Fries .

02. Developing a heat-resistant potato variety

The Department of Agriculture is currently developing a potato variety called “Red-la Soda” as a heat-resistant variety focusing on the potato cultivation in Jaffna and kalpitiya like areas.

03. Maintaining cold storage for seedling of potatoes

During the past, the seed potatoes were stored in the farm on grounds before delivering them to the seed potato propagation center. Department of Agriculture now has developed over 150 MT capacity of cold storage to store the seed potato to ensure quality propagation.

04. Maintaining “zero balance stock”

In order to reduce the post harvest losses of potatoes, a system called “zero balance stock” was established by a local small scale company, which means the harvesting of potatoes is only done for orders, so that the maintaining of a stock is no need.

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